

SEARCH REPORTS AS A WAY TO MAKE THE (ACADEMIC) SEARCH PROCESS AND INFORMATION EVALUATION COMPREHENSIBLE AND TRANSPARENT

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Abstract

Bibliography and literature review are key elements and important quality criteria of scholarly publications. However, they do not provide contextual information on the search process that led to the used sources. Yet, the search process is in itself an essential element of academic work. The proposed paper discusses the importance of visibility of the information search process within scholarly work and suggests a search report for the integration of further contextual information.

WHY LITERATURE REVIEW AND BIBLIOGRAPHY IS NOT ENOUGH

Academic publications are unthinkable without references and footnotes, as they prove statements, acknowledge previous work, and enable verification and replication of research. They help to assess the up-to-date-ness and depth of a contribution and are thereby also an important criterion to assess the quality of a publication. References also serve as a 'roadmap' for future research, guiding scholars to subsequent relevant literature.

In addition to the references, key publications are presented and discussed in the literature review, and thus also set in relation to each other.

However, these approaches do not provide any information on how the used resources relate to the research process and how they were found. This means, for example, that catalogs or (academic) search engines that were used to find central or particularly important publications cannot be identified.

THE CONTEXT OF SOURCES AND (RE-) SEARCH PROCESS

The importance of the search process within scholarly work

Especially in a scholarly context, the search process and the selection of the used sources are a central part of the research. Additional information on the choice of sources thereby helps to further strengthen the comprehensibility.

Furthermore, the (re-)search itself is also part of the results of scholarly work. Marchionini considers the search process as such as a result, as the experiences and mental reflections also become part of the seeker's knowledge. [1]

This lack of context of sources, search process and re-search process could be solved by a search report.

The search report

In addition to the bibliography and the literature review, academic papers could be supported by a search report that provides details on the information search and names the main platforms, catalogs, repositories, and search engines, that have been used. This way, in addition to the sources themselves, the way and access to them would also be highlighted. [2]

Besides greater visibility of the search process and more transparency, this makes it also easier to assess the comprehensiveness of the literature research. Moreover, important repositories for a topic could be emphasized.

The use of AI tools could also be mentioned in a search report. For example, prompts that were used, could be listed, and be thereby presented in a comprehensible and visible way.

Overall, the inclusion of a search report would not only strengthen the integrity and transparency of a publication, but also contribute to advancing research standards. This would also be a more transparent approach to information search within a scholarly context and help to further promote search literacy.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Marchionini, *Information Seeking in Electronic Environments*, Cambridge, MA, USA: Cambridge University Press, 1995, p. 47f.
- [2] A. Neovesky, "Suche und Relevanz in digitalen wissenschaftlichen Sammlungen – Eine Untersuchung zu Suchstrategien, Auswahlverhalten und Digital Literacy von Historiker*innen", Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Computer Philology and Medieval Studies, TU Darmstadt, 2023, urn:nbn:de:tuda-tuprints-240718, p. 280.